

Original Article

Empowering Women in Agriculture: A Study on Women's Involvement in Agricultural and Livestock Management in Rural Pakistan

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This research focuses on the role of rural women in agriculture and livestock management, their involvement and empowerment in Tehsil Tandlianwala, District Faisalabad, Punjab Pakistan. The study explores the role of the socio-economic environment in which women are vested with some power to participate in agricultural activities. The data was collected among 160 rural women through a quantitative survey.

The results show that rural women engage in several agricultural activities especially on livestock keeping, with high contribution when it comes to milking, feeding and animal care. The obstacles faced by them were social structural barriers, which included patriarchy gender norms and limited decision-making power at household level. The research has shown that education and household income are critical determinants of the level of women's empowerment in agricultural decision making

The study ends by highlighting the importance of gender targeted policies, increase access to training and financial credit and cultural intervention in improving involvement and empowerment of rural women in agriculture. Recommendations for future research include investigating the role of men in securing women's empowerment and assessing the influence of microfinance programmes on women participation in agriculture.

Keywords: Agriculture women, farming, issues, rural Punjab, empowerment, challenges

INTRODUCTION

The contribution of women to agricultural sector has remained significant, particularly in the developing countries like Pakistan due to agriculture being the mainstay of rural economy. Rural Pakistani women have historically participated in agricultural activities; however, their roles go unappreciated (Awan et al., 2021). Although they play a major in livestock husbandry and crop production as well as household agricultural practices, rural women are beset with numerous constraints that include limited access to resources and decision-making power, and socio-cultural taboos which suppress their full potential in agriculture transformation.

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Agriculture is the backbone of Pakistan's economy especially in rural areas which comprises majority of the population and have their livelihoods linked to agriculture and livestock. Indeed, the agriculture sector, which contributes substantially to Gross Domestic Product (GDP), approximately 24% of Pakistan's GDP is attributed by agriculture and more than 40% of labor force employed in this sector that are mainly women from rural areas (GoP, 2021). However, women farmers in rural areas of Pakistan make significant contributions but there are a many social, economic and cultural constraints that demotivate them to involve fully in agricultural activities. The role of women in agriculture (livestock management, crop production and post-harvest processing) is crucial for the domestic economy (Kausar et al, 2022). But its acknowledgment of their work and role is restricted, challenging their economic security and the extent to which they can take meaningful decisions.

Women in rural Pakistan have traditionally participated at all levels of agriculture including crop farming and managing livestock (Awan et al., 2021). Studies also reveal that women in rural Pakistan put more hours of work on agricultural activities compared to men. For instance, women are intensely engaged in sowing, weeding, feeding livestock, milking and taking care about the animals including also looking after small ruminates like goats and poultry (Iqbal et al., 2022). Research has shown that women in fact put in more hours on the farm than men, despite their extra domestic duties. For instance, Awan et al. (2021) found time spent (10 h/day by rural women, significantly higher than for men). However, with this high rate of participation, their contributions to agriculture have gone largely ever unnoticed and they as individuals are misunderstood (Shahbaz et al, 2022).

Poor rural women are further disenfranchised by social and cultural norms that restrict their ability to access resources and opportunities for economic and social improvement. One of the major constraining factors to rural women's empowerment is their limited access to learning and training. According to Naz et al. (2018), literacy rate of rural women is way behind as compared to men's, and about 80% of the rural women are illiterate in Pakistan. The issue of illiteracy among women has resulted in their inability to acquire modern agricultural skills, handle livestock effectively and increase their productivity (Iqbal, 2022; Zubair et al, 2023). And socially, the barriers to having women included in high-level decision-making also still grew. In most rural communities, men are more in control on agricultural-related decisions and this limits women's autonomy and access to resources, such as credit, land, and veterinary services (Khan et al., 2024; Raza et al, 2022; Zafar et al, 2024).

According to studies, if women are provided access to education and resources, their capacity and participation in agricultural labor grows manifold. Mahmud et al. (2012), women empowerment in rural area is linked to their capacity to make decision on agriculture practice and this has impact on household income and that of the community. Iqbal et al. (2021) also stressed that investing in women in agriculture can lead to positive household economic impacts since women tend to re-invest their income in their family and community. In contrast, Awan et al. (2021) emphasize here that the use of women in livestock management is an important strategy to increase family income, especially through sales channels of dairy products such as milk, butter and yogurt, which are irreplaceable sources of household income in rural areas.

Although women play an essential role in agriculture, the challenges they face are varied and complex. Awan et al. (2021) indicate that rural women have low access to veterinary services, technical training and credit. If these women do not receive training or if they don't acquire new agricultural practices and modern methods for managing livestock, then there is no way productivity can be increased. Iqbal (2022), underlines this, maintains that women in rural Pakistan are frequently unable to take advantage of loans or subsidies for agriculture, necessary for enlarging their activities and ameliorating the economic position.

Socio-cultural hindrances also influence women involvement in agriculture. Khan et al. (2024) posit that 'embedded' cultural roles of women in the gender division of labor generally inhibit their participation in some agricultural activities such as decision making and land management. Women in most of rural areas

do household activities and childcare while men make decisions on agriculture and land ownership. Such gendered division of labor imposes limitation on the extent to which women can engage in agriculture and consequently restrict their potential empowerment (Awan et al., 2021; Hamza & Sherazi, 2024).

Recent studies have highlighted the need to overcome these social-cultural constraints towards women's emancipation in agriculture. Ijaz et al, (2021) mention that access to resources, including education, training and credit, may need to combine with traditional gender role shifts in order to develop the capacity of rural women and improve their involvement in agriculture decision-making. Batool and Afzal (2021) argue that it is not just about economic dependence but rather their ability to have a say in their lives, notably within the household and community.

This paper will try to fill this gap by exploring the contemporary status and contribution of rural women towards agriculture-livestock management in the backdrop of socio-economic, cultural impediments particularly in Pakistan. This research will communicate to the policy in terms of key constraints and enablers for women empowerment in agriculture, by which the policy can address on how to enhance rural women farmers' Livelihoods and socio-economic status in Pakistan.

REVIEW OF RELATED LITERATURE

Literature emphasize multifarious operations of rural women in agriculture e.g. cultivation and rearing. Research has found that female labour force is around 60 % mostly to livestock like Cow milking, cleaning and taking care of animals (Awan et al., 2021; Hussain, 2022; Qayum et al, 2023). But you wouldn't know it from policy and agricultural development agendas.

According to Naz et al. (2018) had also identified that rural women of Pakistan face several socio-economic constraints which include limited financial resources, declining opportunity for education and training that limit their participation in modernizing agricultural practices. Furthermore, Awan et al. (2021), the livestock business of rural women is restricted by inadequate veterinary services and dimes reservation markets for agricultural products. Iqbal (2022) adds further evidence to these claims by stating that cultural attitudes of women and their roles in agriculture stem from patriarchal ideologies which make them decision-less even when, in the practical field, they contribute a lot to farming.

Recent works like Khan et al (2024), also suggest that rural women empowerment in Pakistan is closely related to how much they participate in farming decision making and the extent which this contributes towards improving the living standard of these women. However, as Iqbal et al. (2021) have become more acknowledged as agricultural producers, their role in higher level decisions is often constrained by patriarchal traditions defining rural communities.

Research Gap

The role of women in agriculture has been well documented in the available literature, especially their significant role in agricultural livestock management. Although, little is known on the detailed sociocultural and economic barriers which inhibit rural women access to agriculture. Although a few studies have examined the constraints against which women perform agricultural tasks, limited research covers how these constraints interact with empowerment, decision making and access to resources. This research seeks to address this gap by offering empirical evidence on the social, economic and cultural factors shaping empowerment of rural women in agriculture.

Research Objectives

The principal objectives of this study are:

1. To determine the level of involvement of women in agriculture and husbandry practices in rural areas Pakistan.
2. To study the social and economic determinants as a cause of their participation in agriculture.
3. To explore the main constraints experienced by women in rural areas who manage livestock and farming practices.
4. To determine socio-cultural factors influencing empowerment of rural women in agriculture.

Research Questions

The following are the research questions of this work:

1. How much are rural women involved in livestock and agriculture activities in Pakistan?
2. What are the key socio-economic variables determining women participation in rural agriculture?
3. What are the main limitations of rural women in livestock farming?
4. What does societal attitude have to do with women empowerment in agriculture?

RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

This quantitative research is conducted to analyze the involvement and empowerment of women in agricultural and livestock related activities of Tehsil Tandlianwala, District Faisalabad, Pakistan. This study utilized a multi-stage sampling method to survey rural women who engaged in agricultural activities. The approach includes the elements:

Study Area

The research was carried out in Tehsil Tandlianwala of Faisalabad District (Central Punjab) Pakistan. This study area was selected based on a well-established agricultural history and the involvement of rural women in crop and animal husbandry. The diverse social and cultural values and economic conditions in that region made it an easier to study the effects of stigma (Naseer, 2021).

Details of Sampling

Several stages sampling method was used. Sampling The sample procedure took place as for the following:

- **Stage 1:** Tehsil Tandlianwala was selected because of the researchers' familiarity with the area and its agricultural significance.
- **Stage 2:** Two UCs (UC-95 and UC-96) were randomly selected from tehsil, and four villages (two from each UC).
- **Stage 3:** We obtained a list of agri-working women in each village. From this list 20 individuals were chosen at random from each of the villages for a total of 160 respondents.

This sampling technique allows for rural women from various communities of tehsil to be sampled in diversity and helps to capture more complete data.

Data Collection

Information was collected employing a structured interview schedule comprising of several socio-economic variables such as:

- **Demographic characteristics:** Age, marital status, educational level and household size.
- **Participation in agriculture:** Data on women's involvement in rearing of livestock, cultivation and household agricultural activities.
- **Constraints experienced:** Issues such as accessing resources, training, veterinary services, credit and overarching socio-cultural limitations that bind women's participation in agricultural decision making.

All surveys were administered by trained interviewers who were fluent in the local language and familiar with the culture (including late adolescents) to avoid misunderstanding or bias.

Data Analysis

The survey data was analyzed through the descriptive and inferential statistical procedures with software, SPSS (Statistical Package for Social Sciences). The analysis procedures included:

- **Descriptive statistics:** Frequencies and percentages were used to summarize participant demographics and the degree of women's involvement in agricultural activities while means and standard deviations were calculated for all other explanatory variables.
- **T-test and Chi-square test:** Used to compare participation levels of men and women in agricultural activities and to determine the significance of the differences in socio-economic factors that influence women's participation.
- **Cross-tabulation** was used to explore the association between the socio-economic variables of age, education and income levels with women participating in such agricultural practices.

The findings from such analysis were used as approximations to make inferences about socio-economic influences upon female participation in agriculture and constraints, which inhibit women empowerment.

Results and Interpretation

Data for the study was collected and analyzed in descriptive statistics as well as inferential analysis to bring out trends, relationships, differences between rural women participation in agriculture and livestock activities. The analysis provides some important insights into the roles and constraints of women and the socio-economic determinants.

Participation in Agricultural Activities

The results reveal that the rural women are heavily engaged in several agricultural and livestock operations. Frequency and duration were the indicators of participation. The results of the responses on female involvement in different agricultural activities are presented in below table.

Table 1. *Distribution of the Respondents by their Involvement in Agricultural Activities*

<i>Activity</i>	<i>Mostly</i> (%)	<i>Occasionally</i>	<i>Not at All</i>
Fodder Cutting	68.1	14.4	17.5
Weeding Practices	41.0	43.8	15.6
Harvesting	36.9	30.0	33.1
Binding	40.6	22.5	36.9
Threshing	7.5	20.0	72.5
Drying	10.0	26.9	63.1
Storage of Seeds	14.0	12.5	73.8
Selling Agricultural Products	7.0	14.4	78.8

This table shows that the percentage participation is highest in fodder cutting (68.1%) and weeding (41%) and harvesting (36.9%) groups and lowest in selling of agricultural products (7%).

Participation in Livestock Activities

Women's participation in livestock husbandry was also analyzed. Participation in different livestock activities is presented in the following Table.

Table 2. *Distribution of the respondents according to whether they are involved in livestock activities.*

<i>Livestock Activity</i>	<i>Mostly</i> (%)	<i>Occasionally</i>	<i>Not at All</i>
Cleaning Sheds	43.8	42.5	13.8
Watering Animals	38.1	34.4	27.5
Milking	37.5	25.0	37.5
Ghee Preparation	34.4	38.1	27.5
Egg Collection	25.0	29.4	45.6
Grazing Animals	8.8	11.3	80.0
Feeding Animals	42.5	38.8	18.8

The table indicates that cleaning of animal sheds (43.8), feeding animals(42.5) and watering of animals (38.1) are the activities in which rural women contribute most, while grazing of animals (8.8) showed minimum participation declaration by them. "This emphasizes the significant contribution of women in the aspects related to domestic livestock handling.

Restrictions and Limitations for Women

The research also discovered the major factors constraining women's active participation in agriculture and management of livestock. The key difficulties faced by rural women are:

- **Veterinary services costs:** A lot of women mentioned the cost of taking animals to a veterinarian as a major constraint, implying that they were unable to address animal health in a satisfactory manner.

- **Limited Access to Training and Learning Opportunities:** Many women felt they were not receiving enough opportunity for training in modern farming methods and husbandry extended (livestock) management and therefore could not improve their productivity.
- **Limited access to credit:** Access to finance was further limiting factor, due to women's low level of financial independence, investment in livestock improvement and agriculture is reduced.
- **Culture and social norms:** Socio-cultural barriers, including traditional gender roles, and lack of decision-making authority were also identified as important factors that inhibited full women engagement in agriculture.

Statistical Analysis

The association between socio-economic factors and involvement of women in agriculture and livestock were analyzed using chi-square tests and correlation coefficients. The results indicated that:

- **Education:** Educated women had an involvement in agricultural decisions-making but at low overall time as compared to illiterate women. This implies that illiterate women are likely to engage longer in farm activities even if they may not have encountered modern agriculture practices.
- **Relationship:** Married women appear to be more engaged on livestock management than single women due to cultural beliefs and family obligations.
- **Size of the Households:** Women in relatively bigger size households had more involvement towards agricultural, especially livestock management because generally they were responsible for feeding and caring of larger strength.

Table 3. *The Relationship Between the Socio-Economic Factors and Women Participation in the Livestock Management*

Factor	Correlation Coefficient	p-value
Education Level	0.324	0.000**
Marital Status	0.292	0.003*
Household Size	0.178	0.056
Income	0.225	0.014*

This table shows correlations of education level ($r= 0.324$, $p<0.05$), marital status ($r= 0.292$, $p=<0.05$) and income ($r= 0.225$, $p<0.05$) with participation of women in livestock management.

Discussion

The results of this research provide important insight into the role of rural women in agriculture and livestock management in Tehsil Tandlianwala, District Faisalabad Pakistan. Rural women in Pakistan's agriculture also remain an important stakeholder as significant contributors to household incomes and local economy. But despite significant efforts, they are often restrained by social norms, restricted access to resources and gender bias.

Women's Involvement in Farm and Livestock Management

The study results attest that rural woman are actively participating in agriculture, particularly in livestock management. Thus, it can be said that women in Tehsil Tandlianwala invest a significant amount of time in tasks like milking animals, feeding, watering and caring the animals is consistent with the finding of other studies where women would spend most of their time in livestock as well crop related activities. According to Awan et al. (2021) have also reported that in rural Punjab, females spend longer time than men on livestock activities with main emphasis on time consuming and daily activities like feeding, watering of animals. This work confirms these findings with 42.5% of women in this study area reporting being actively involved in these activities.

It also reveals that women's participation in the livestock sector is generally higher than men's, and not limited to poultry, in Pakistan. As noted by Iqbal (2022), rural women are a driving force for livestock sector in several parts of Pakistan. They control not only small such as goats and chickens but also, they have substantial influence and inputs on the large herds. This is yet supported by the findings of this study where women in Tehsil Tandlianwala possess 52.7% larger livestock holdings from male gender at birth Furnishings of cows, goats and sheep. This pattern indicates women's significantly high contribution in up-keeping of livestock-based livelihood systems, especially when they directly contribute to household income and food security.

Constraints Faced by Rural Women

One of the most startling revelations from the report is regarding gender related facts in agricultural and livestock management. The barriers that were revealed – namely, high cost of veterinary services and lack of training for the dog handlers, limited financial access/utilization and cultural restrictions are very similar to the ones reported from previous studies. Awan et al. (2021) and Khan et al. (2024) emphasize difficult access to veterinary services for the rural women due to high cost of animal care, and limited presence of vet service in distant rural areas. These limitations limit access and undermine successful livestock management and productivity improvements, exposing these herders to higher health risks for animals and lower economic returns.

Another serious limitation is the lack of access to training and modern agricultural information. Iqbal (2022) pointed out, women in rural Pakistan have very limited access to agricultural training which can have a great impact on their productivity and adoption of modern farming practices. This document agrees with that view by confirming that many women in the study area had not received training in advanced animal husbandry practices. Naz et al. (2018), women in agriculture have less exposure to formal training and education as opposed to their male counterparts, which makes them less capable of improving the practice of agriculture thus maintaining the circle of poverty in rural areas.

The study also identified sociocultural obstacles to women, especially the limitation on decision making within a household. In most rural parts of Pakistan, women are regarded as home makers – they are assigned roles of handling the household chores while men play key roles in decision making whether about agriculture or any other area. Kabeer (1999) and Malhotra and Schuler (2014) contend that most women are not able to actively engage in economic or social decision-making, even within industries where their involvement is extensive. This concern is also evident in the current study as many women in Tehsil Tandlianwala were frustrated with having little to say about what happens on the farm, even though they work hard there and claim ownership of land. Khan et al. (2024) further buttress this by stating that the contribution of women to agriculture is largely underestimated, and often, their role in decision-making is hampered due to conventional gender norms.

Socio-Economic Factors Influencing Women's Empowerment

Besides, the impact of socio-economic factors (such as education, household income and marital status) on women's involvement in agriculture was also investigated. Education was found to be a strong evidence-based predictor of women empowerment in the present study. Naz et al. (2018) and Mahmud et al. (2012) have also reported that women with higher level of education are more likely to make decisions and engage in those agricultural activities which demand professional knowledge. The same conclusion was arrived at in a related study which found higher levels of education to increase the likelihood of women participating in making decisions regarding crop production on farm resources and care of livestock, reiterating the importance of education for empowering women to participate in agriculture (Ajayi et al., 2017).

The household income results are consistent with Iqbal (2022) which indicates that women involvement in agriculture is positively related to the economic condition of the households. Women from the wealthier households had greater access to resources (and technology) which made them more productive in agricultural production. This study has also shown that wealthier women are more likely to participate in livestock activities and have access to veterinary care and inputs.

Women's marital status was another significant contributor to participation. Everything else being equal, married women were more engaged in farming activities compared with wifehood women, specifically in livestock care. This result is consistent with those of Rehman et al. (2020), who suggest that married women are often more engaged in agriculture because of the shared nature of family work on farms. It is, however, participation which comes at a cost to personal autonomy; women's decision-making with regard to agriculture is often constrained in the face of domestic and marital obligations.

Gender Division of Labor and Empowerment

The has also work only in gendered roles of agricultural rural settings. On women's involvement in livestock activities Traditional foci of gender roles define men as people who take high profile decisions and are also perceived to be owners of cattle and small stock, whereas women are regarded as the employees' infantries, through which they engage more in low skill intensive tasks. This gender division of work is entrenched in historical patriarchal relations, underlying how a woman's autonomy in the agricultural economy is restricted. These gender norms, according to Chambers and Momsen (2007), limit women's access to resources and authority, a theme that also emerged in this paper. While women play an important part in agricultural and livestock production, their economic contribution is not proportionally reflected in decision-making power or recognition within the agricultural policy framework.

Conclusion

This research was conducted to assess the performance, share and empowerment of the rural women in agriculture and livestock management practices in Tehsil Tandlianwala District Faisalabad, Pakistan. Our study findings emphasize the rural women's involvement in farming, cattle rearing and livestock practices that are significant to conserve at small scale for sustaining rural people's living source. Though at the very core of significant agricultural operations, rural women still have some socio-economic-cultural constraints that diminish their potential to manifest themselves more effectively in agrarian life.

The study revealed that women are involved in on-farm work such as chopping of fodder and milking among others. But even they are mostly limited to manual labor, often with little control over their own households or the running of the farm. Exclusion from autonomy and leadership in agriculture Women are crushed by male-oriented customs and the sexual division of labour which determines their choices for autonomy and leadership in agricultural decision making.

The literature review also highlights some critical obstacles to empowering women in agriculture. This includes poor access to education/training, expensive veterinary services, lack of capital and an unfavorable credit environment. Therefore, limitations like this keep going back where women cannot use modern agriculture and therefore stay in their poverty cycle, in the rural areas. Education was identified as one of the strongest correlations that influenced women's role in making different agronomic/farming decisions and their general empowerment. Educated women were more self-esteemed and had higher voice on farm management hence, the importance of education programs for rural women empowerment.

Furthermore, the research also expands women's empowerment literature particularly in the context of rural Pakistan by highlighting the socio-cultural factors that affect women participation in agriculture. This is in line with other research that has also emphasized that empowerment could not be equated merely with economic approaches but as a social and political dimension. When women's ability to equally

participate in agriculture is increased, it involves overcoming gender-specific constraints by providing them with the resources, skills and support necessary for their success at both household- and farm-based levels.

Implications of the Study

The findings of our study have significant implications for the role of rural women in agriculture and livestock, particularly in rural Pakistan. Focusing on social and economic and social hurdles that women face. The implications of the findings are significant for policy makers, development practitioners and gender advocates.

1. **Education for Empowerment** : The significance of education to the empowerment of women is also underscored by this rural-based study. Highly educated women are less likely to engage in agricultural decisions, use modern farming techniques and have productivity. This is an indication for education policy interventions with rural women in enhancing knowledge level in agriculture to facilitate better decisions at household level.
2. **Policy and resource allocation**: The study shows that lack of veterinary services, financial resources as well as agricultural training were major constraints for women's involvement in animal husbandry. Findings indicate the necessity to develop gender-sensitive policies that can break through these barriers, configuring financial instruments dedicated to women or facilitating their access to credit and proposing training actions adapted to-wards the needs and reality of rural women.
3. **Cultural Transformation and Social Norms**: The socio-cultural factors inhibiting women active participation in agricultural decision-making is an essential part of this study. It shall help facilitate shift in cultural values and gender norms to enable women to equally participate in both agriculture development and economic decision making with men. This requires community-level interventions, focused on raising awareness and achieving gender equity in rural settings.
4. **Recognition of Women Work**: It is also reiterated in this study to recognize that women's work is carried out in agriculture and animal husbandry. Women are mostly missing in these sectors and their roles not included in economic policies. The study suggests that data should be collected and women's agricultural labor documented to ensure it is increasingly recognized as a contribution that should be compensated in future policy discussions and economic planning.

Recommendations for Future Researchers

- **Geographical Coverage**: District Faisalabad, Tehsil Tandlianwala and however it is suggested to extend the coverage for other rural areas of Pakistan in future study. Future studies could be done to compare rural women of different provinces like Sindh, Khyber Pakhtunkhwa and Balochistan which may provide more comprehensive insights into empowerment of women in agriculture at diverse socio-cultural background.
- **Longitudinal Research**: Longitudinal research that track women and their level of empowerment over time will be helpful to examine how programs (e.g. education, training, support) influence the degree of participation by women in agriculture. This would also enable to reveal long-term effects and add to the understanding of how sustainable such empowerment initiatives truly are.
- **Exploring the Role of Technology**: Further studies may be carried out to investigate technology in empowering rural women involved in agriculture. Digital technologies and agricultural innovations may offer women greater access to information, training and markets that could raise productivity and decision-making for them. Research may explore the influence of digital literacy and e-agriculture tools on women's involvement in agricultural practices and economic independence.
- **The Role of Men in Empowerment**: This study has mainly focused on women empowerment, but the role of men for promotion or hinderance in women empowerment in agriculture is a topic for future research. If men's attitudes for gender equality and women's role in agriculture could be understood,

it could inform development of community-based interventions to contribute to broadly engaging both women and men in the work required to change norms around gender and equity in agricultural practices.

- **Quantitative and Qualitative Mix:** This was a quantitative study; however, future studies could combine quantitative assessment with qualitative interviews and focus group discussions. This would enable a better comprehension of the socio-cultural context impacting women's role in agriculture and offer greater insight into rural women's specific experiences and perspectives of empowerment.
- **Studying the Effects of Microfinance:** The literature has also proposed microfinance as an important vehicle to improve the status of rural women. For further research, one area of attention could be towards the exploration of microcredit programs' contribution to women's involvement in agriculture including livestock management and small-scale farming. They could be used to investigate the degree that access to credit affects women's ability to increase productivity and gain economic freedom.

Policy Analysis

Further studies might look at the impact of policies to empower rural women in agriculture. Information concerning how policies on land tenure, access to financial services, and agricultural subsidies work in rural areas—and the extent to which these policies affect women's empowerment and economic participation—could be investigated. "This may be able to shed light on deficiencies in policy enforcement, as well as facilitate more effectively informed policymaking

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